

EXTRUSION OF ENDLESS FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC ELASTOMER COMPOSITES WITH CRIMPED P-ARAMID FIBER

Johannes Gattinger¹, Benedikt Kirchebner² and Michael Kirsch³

¹ Institute of Medical and Polymer Engineering, Technical University of Munich, Germany, johannes.gattinger@tum.de, www.medtech.mw.tum.de

² Institute of Medical and Polymer Engineering, Technical University of Munich, Germany, benedikt.kirchebner@tum.de, www.medtech.mw.tum.de

³ Institute of Medical and Polymer Engineering, Technical University of Munich, Germany, michael.kirsch@tum.de, www.medtech.mw.tum.de

Keywords: Thermoplastic elastomer, Crimped fiber, Composite rope, Extrusion, Aramid fiber

ABSTRACT

In this study, the extrusion of flexible composites with elastomeric matrix and endless crimped fibers was investigated. Flexible composites made of elastomeric matrix and wavy fibers combine high strength and high elongation. These materials show a J-shaped stress-strain curve that allows high flexibility but with an elongation limitation and a stiffening of the composite that occurs when the fibers become straightened. This mechanical behavior is common in biomaterials such as skin or tendons. Aim of this study was to get such composite parts via standard thermoplastic extrusion process.

1 INTRODUCTION

Flexible composites consist of elastomeric matrix and reinforcement elements with the effect of a much higher deformation range than conventional composites with a thermosetting or thermoplastic matrix [1]. Tires, hoses and conveyor belts are typical examples for established flexible composites. These flexible composites allow large deflection but no large expansion. To reach flexible composites, that allow also large expansion, Chou and Takahashi [2] proposed the use of either short fibers or fibers in wavy pattern. Such composites made of elastomeric matrix and wavy fibers show a J-shaped stress-strain relationship. Under low loading, these composites show high elongation and low stiffness. With increased loading, the composite stiffens and high strength could be reached. Chou et al. [1-3] recommended laminates of wavy fibers and elastomeric matrix and presented mathematical models to calculate the nonlinear elastic behavior of such laminates. Monleon Pradas and Diaz Calleja [4, 5] suggested sinusoidal fiber reinforced elastomers for reproduction of some mechanical features of tendons and ligaments which show J-shaped stress-strain functions [6]. Iannace and Ambrosio [7, 8] proposed elastomer hoses reinforced with helically shaped fibers as artificial tendons. Some research was done on laminates from elastomeric matrix and knitted fabrics by Huang and Ramakrishna [9, 10] and Bekisli and Nied [11]. Recently Jang et al. [12] presented a flexible composite sheet from elastomer reinforced with networks of wavy fibers with similar mechanical properties than human epidermis. So far, not much effort was done to develop industrial processes for the fabrication of flexible composites with wavy fiber reinforcement. Aim of this research was to investigate options to manufacture crimped fiber reinforced elastomers via standard extrusion process.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

As matrix material a transparent thermoplastic elastomer (THERMOLAST® K TF5THT, KRAIBURG TPE GmbH & Co. KG, Waldkraiburg, Germany) with a hardness of 47 Shore A, tensile strength of 5.5 MPa and an elongation at break of 600 % was used. The reinforcing fiber was a high modulus p-aramid fiber roving (Twaron® 2200, linear density 8050 dtex (5000 filaments), Teijin Aramid, Arnhem, NL) with a tensile modulus of 99 GPa and a breaking strength of 2930 MPa that was crimped in a previous step. The fibers were crimped through a heat-setting process. The fiber roving

was wound on a steel mandrel of 1 mm in diameter and then heat-set in a tube furnace (Gero RO 50-250/12, Carbolite Gero GmbH & Co. KG, Neuhausen, Germany) at a temperature of 220 °C and a holding time of 10 minutes. A sleeve-die (Figure 1) and a single screw extruder (Teach-Line® E 20 T, screw diameter 20 mm, Dr. Collin GmbH, Ebersberg, Germany) was used to join and mold matrix and fiber. The resulting strands had a circular cross section with a diameter of 4 mm. To compare specimens with crimped and straight fibers as well as specimens of pure thermoplastic elastomer matrix the prepared fiber rovings consisted of a few meters of uncrimped fiber roving and a few meters of crimped fiber roving. After this roving passed through the process was continued for a while to obtain unreinforced specimens. The extruded strands were cut into specimens with a length of 300 mm.

Figure 1: Sleeve-die to extrude crimped fiber reinforced strands.

To determine the mechanical properties tensile testing was performed (Zwick/Roell Z2.5, Zwick GmbH & Co. KG, Ulm, Germany). The clamping length was 100 mm and the test speed 50 mm/min. The stress-strain curves as well as the maximum reached forces and elongations were evaluated.

3 RESULTS

Extruded specimens of straight reinforced, crimped reinforced and unreinforced thermoplastic elastomer composites are shown in Figure 2. The resulting crimp ratio (difference of uncrimped fiber length (l₁) and crimped fiber length (l₂) divided by the uncrimped fiber length; (l₁-l₂)/l₁) in the composite strands was not that high as expected. During the extrusion process the crimped fiber roving became stretched somewhat so that only a low crimp ratio remained from the initial crimp of the fiber roving.

Figure 3 shows the mechanical behavior of the crimped and straight fiber reinforced specimens as well as the unreinforced specimens. Both reinforced composites show an enhanced strength in comparison to the unreinforced material. A slight J-shape of the composites stress-strain relationship is identifiable, but for both, the straight and crimped reinforced ones, although a little more pronounced by the crimped reinforced strands. The straight fiber reinforced specimens are overall a little stiffer than the crimped fiber reinforced ones. A comparison of the onset points showed a 60 % higher elongation capability of the crimped fiber reinforced specimens than the straight fiber reinforced ones (Figure 4) The crimped fiber reinforced specimens show a significant higher strength and elongation than the straight fiber reinforced specimens (Figure 5).

Figure 2: Extruded strands. a) Straight fiber reinforced composite strand. b) Crimped fiber reinforced composite strand. c) Unreinforced thermoplastic elastomer matrix strand.

Figure 3: Tensile properties of crimped fiber reinforced thermoplastic elastomer compared to straight fiber reinforced thermoplastic elastomer and the pure thermoplastic elastomer matrix. Averaged curves with standard deviation

Figure 4: Onset-points of the slightly J-shaped stress-strain curves

Figure 5: Comparison of maximum force and elongation of the composite specimens

4 DISCUSSION

The stress-strain curve of the crimped fiber reinforced strands showed not a distinct characteristic J-shape due to a too low resulting crimp ratio of the fiber in the composite. It is supposed, that the stretching of the crimped fiber roving in the process resulted from a matrix backflow into the fiber feed. However, the crimped fiber reinforced composite was significant softer with increased strength and elongation compared to the straight fiber reinforced composite. In the tensile tests, the failure of the specimens was always a failure in the fiber-matrix interface. The fiber roving was pulled out the matrix at the clamping point, without a fiber or matrix break. This leads to the assumption, that the composites strength could be enhanced by improving the fiber-matrix adhesion through suitable bonding agents or other methods for adhesion improvement, like plasma treatment.

5 CONCLUSION

It is to state, that thus far the crimped fiber reinforced composite strands could not be fabricated with a wanted distinct J-shape of the stress-strain curves. It is presumed that a higher resulting crimp ratio of the fiber in the composite and therefore a more distinct J-shape could be reached through a geometrical optimization of the sleeve-die (to prevent melt backflow), an optimization of the extrusion parameters (melt temperature, screw speed, haul-off speed), an improvement of the initial crimp of the fiber roving or an adjustment of the matrix viscosity.

Furthermore, it needs to be investigated how the adhesion between fiber and matrix can be improved to enhance the composites strength.

REFERENCES

- [1] Chou, T.-W., Flexible composites. *Journal of Materials Science*, 24 (3), 1989, pp. 761-783, (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/bf01148757>)
- [2] Chou, T.W., Takahashi, K., Non-linear elastic behaviour of flexible fibre composites. *Composites*, 18 (1), 1987, pp. 25-34, ([http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0010-4361\(87\)90004-8](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0010-4361(87)90004-8))
- [3] Kuo, C.-M., Takahashi, K., Chou, T.-W., Effect of Fiber Waviness on the Nonlinear Elastic Behavior of Flexible Composites. *Journal of Composite Materials*, 22 (11), 1988, pp. 1004-1025, (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/002199838802201101>)
- [4] Monleón Pradas, M., Díaz Calleja, R., An extensible modulus-developing polymer composite. *Composites Science and Technology*, 36 (3), 1989, pp. 227-241, ([http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0266-3538\(89\)90022-5](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0266-3538(89)90022-5))
- [5] Monleón Pradas, M., Díaz Calleja, R., Reproduction in a polymer composite of some mechanical features of tendons and ligaments. In: High performance biomaterials: a comprehensive guide to medical and pharmaceutical applications, Szycher M. (Hrsg.), Technomic, Lancaster u.a., 1991, S. 519-23
- [6] Chamberlain, C.S., Jr., R.V., Ligament and Tendon. In: Handbook of Biomaterial Properties, Murphy W., Black J., Hastings G. (Hrsg.), Chapman and Hall, London, 2016, S. 55-62
- [7] Ambrosio, L., De Santis, R., Iannace, S., Netti, P.A., Nicolais, L., Viscoelastic behavior of composite ligament prostheses. *J Biomed Mater Res*, 42 (1), 1998, pp. 6-12, ([https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-4636\(199810\)42:1<6::AID-JBM2>3.0.CO;2-U](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-4636(199810)42:1<6::AID-JBM2>3.0.CO;2-U))
- [8] Iannace, S., Sabatini, G., Ambrosio, L., Nicolais, L., Mechanical behaviour of composite artificial tendons and ligaments. *Biomaterials*, 16 (9), 1995, pp. 675-80, ([https://doi.org/10.1016/0142-9612\(95\)99693-G](https://doi.org/10.1016/0142-9612(95)99693-G))
- [9] Huang, Z.M., Ramakrishna, S., Dinner, H.P., Tay, A.A.O., Characterization of a Knitted Fabric Reinforced Elastomer Composite. *Journal of reinforced plastics and composites*, 18 (2), 1999, pp. 118-137, (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/073168449901800202>)
- [10] Ramakrishna, S., Ming Huang, Z., Yew, H.M., Development of a novel flexible composite material. *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, 89-90, 1999, pp. 473-477, ([http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0924-0136\(99\)00056-4](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0924-0136(99)00056-4))

- [11] Bekisli, B., Nied, H.F., Flexible composites with knitted reinforcements. SPE Annual Technical Conference ANTEC, Boston, 2011, S. 578-583
- [12] Jang, K.I., Chung, H.U., Xu, S., Lee, C.H., Luan, H., Jeong, J., Cheng, H., Kim, G.T., Han, S.Y., Lee, J.W., Kim, J., Cho, M., Miao, F., Yang, Y., Jung, H.N., Flavin, M., Liu, H., Kong, G.W., Yu, K.J., Rhee, S.I., Chung, J., Kim, B., Kwak, J.W., Yun, M.H., Kim, J.Y., Song, Y.M., Paik, U., Zhang, Y., Huang, Y., Rogers, J.A., Soft network composite materials with deterministic and bio-inspired designs. *Nat Commun*, 6, 2015, pp. 6566, (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1038/ncomms7566>)